

Theoretical and Practical Basics of English Teaching

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Annotation:

Main theories of English teaching and effective methods of practicing them , by the end of the session participants will have ,reflected on teaching and learning English, practiced and discussed different techniques for teaching English.

Key words: Particular, history, difficulties, Comparative Teaching Methodologies, Ancient Greek, Direct Method, Silent Way.

Teaching came into its own as a profession in the last century. Central to this process was the emergence of the concept of methods of language teaching. The method concept in language teaching-the notion of a systematic set of teaching practices based on a particular theory of language and language learning-is a powerful one, and the quest for better methods preoccupied teachers and applied linguists throughout the 20th century. The history of changes in language teaching throughout history, up through the Direct Method in the 20th century. One of the most lasting legacies of the Direct Method has been the notion of method itself. in language teaching has been characterized in a variety of ways. A more or less classical formulation suggests that methodology links theory and practice. Within methodology a distinction is often made between methods and approaches, in which methods are held to be fixed teaching systems with prescribed techniques and practices, and approaches are language teaching philosophies that can be interpreted and applied in a variety of different ways in the classroom.

This distinction is probably best seen as a continuum ranging from highly prescribed methods to loosely described approaches. years the imperative need of using a foreign language appears in all areas of a science, manufacture and culture present practice of teaching foreign languages there are some typical problems forcing the teacher to address to experience of the colleagues, to innovative

ideas, to a science these problems, difficulties and lacks of a traditional technique of teaching there are the following basic problems:

- low authority of a subject because of shortages of a present technique of teaching.
- low intensity of pupils speech activity.
- superficiality in forming of base skills and haste of transition from reproductive to productive kinds of work.
- absence of good practical recommendations on elimination and the prevention of gaps in pupils knowledge and skills.
- weakness of existing system of appreciation of pupils work.

Spontaneity of a choice and application of evident support, their low didactic efficiency of methods of teaching have shown, that all named problems will effectively solved, if we apply elaborations of various innovators for amplification of a traditional technique of teaching that can increase essentially quality of teaching foreign (in particular English) language.

1. Comparative Teaching Methodologies

The very first definition of methodology was given by E.M. Ryt in 1930, who wrote that the methodology of teaching foreign languages is a practical application of comparative linguistics. A similar position had A.V. Scherba. Emergence of views on the methodology as applied linguistics, was due to the fact that the method 30-s not enough to identify the specificity of a foreign language as a subject, and there was no developed system of research methods, without which there can be no true science. Direction in determining the methodology as a science, connected with the name

B.V. Belyaev, who believed that the technique is nothing like applied psychology. However, a number of problems methods, in particular, the selection of material, especially the use of techniques and ways of working, depending on the audience, cannot be resolved based only on psychology. Therefore, this definition of techniques did not spread. The late 30-s - early 40-ies

starts take shape, one more line - definition of methodology as pedagogical science. Do pedagogy and methodology, there is one object of study - the processes of learning, education, goals and objectives of training, education and maintenance items. Uniform and research methods are, therefore, the determination method as a science teacher was a step forward to its registration as an independent science. Direction in determining the methodology as a science began in the late 40-s. The method is recognized by science, which has its own laws and its methods. The most complete definition of the method reads: Methods of teaching is the science, exploring the aims and content, pattern, means, methods, techniques and training systems, as well as studying the processes of teaching and training material on a foreign language.

The beginning of XX century there was also another problem. That was the problem of method. It was quite natural, since after 1917 new school demanded the application of new techniques. At that time, advocated direct (natural) method. It was believed that this method was based on a correct principle - associating foreign words with the objects themselves. This was the method of natural (associative) learning a foreign language, which was the most economical, fastest-reaching goal is this being promoted direct method, when the West is having the idea of mixed method? This was due to several reasons. First, in the royal schools dominated the grammar- translation and textual-translation methods based on cramming, from which it was necessary to be free. Direct same method against them was more progressive, as proceeded from the living language of speech training, as the primary means of language functioning., only direct method of instruction intended to communicate., education was not familiar with the proposals of other methods that have arisen in the West after the World War I, because this war, and then the civil, broke all contact.

Time, not only the goal of learning a foreign language changed, and claims to ownership of them. Methods of teaching foreign languages were in crisis. Always requires radical change. Thus, in low productive ideas were made the transition to communicative teaching. The crisis revived the active and methodical search, which contributed to the development of modern teaching concepts of foreign language teaching: Communicative (I.L. Beem, E. I. Passov), intensive (G.A. Kitaygorodskaya), activity (Ilyasov) and others.

Though there is no one correct approach, most teachers usually find themselves more comfortable using one or the other of the approaches listed and described. Though there is nothing overtly wrong with this, it must be remembered that students differ greatly, not just in age but also in mentality, thus they may respond differently to any given approach to language teaching. Because of different learning styles, the effective teacher must be prepared to adapt his or her teaching to the needs and preferences of each class. Our advice is to 'find yourself' with respect to the approaches listed below. That said, don't be afraid to experiment with and/or adapt your style of teaching. In the end, you may discover that the best approach is eclectic in nature and includes bits of this and bits of that.as to give some depth of understanding as to the evolution of ideas that has marked the emergence of newer and different approaches to language teaching, we have tried to place the following list of methodological approaches in chronological order.

Grammar Translation Method

Ancient Greek are known as "dead languages", based on the fact that people no longer speak them for the purpose of interactive communication. Yet they are still acknowledged as important languages to learn (especially Latin) for the purpose of gaining access to classical literature, and up until fairly recently, for the kinds of grammar training that led to the "mental dexterity" considered so important in any higher education study stream has been studied for centuries, with the prime objectives of learning how to read classical Latin texts, understanding the fundamentals of grammar and translation, and gaining insights into some important foreign influences Latin has had on the development of other European languages. The method used to teach it overwhelmingly bore those

objectives in mind, and came to be known as the Classical Method. It is now more commonly known in Foreign Language Teaching circles as the Grammar Translation Method. It is hard to decide which is more surprising - the fact that this method has survived right up until today, or the fact that what was essentially a method developed for the study of "dead" languages involving little or no spoken communication or listening comprehension is still used for the study of languages that are very much "alive" and require competence not only in terms of reading, writing and structure, but also speaking, listening and interactive communication.

Direct Method

The end of the late 1800s, a revolution in language teaching philosophy took place that is seen by many as the "dawn" of modern foreign language teaching. Teachers, frustrated by the limits of the Grammar Translation Method in terms of its inability to create "communicative" competence in students, began to experiment with new ways of teaching language. Basically, teachers began attempting to teach foreign languages in a way that was more similar to first language acquisition. It incorporated techniques designed to address all the areas that the Grammar Translation did not - namely oral communication, more spontaneous use of the language, and developing the ability to "think" in the target language. Perhaps in an almost reflexive action, the method also moved as far away as possible from various techniques typical of the Grammar Translation Method - for instance using L1 as the language of instruction, memorizing grammatical rules and lots of translation between L1 and the target language. Appearance of the "Direct Method" thus coincided with a new school of thinking that dictated that all foreign language teaching should occur in the target language only, with no translation and an emphasis on linking meaning to the language being learned.

The method became very popular during the first quarter of the 20th century, especially in private language schools in Europe where highly motivated students could study new languages and not need to travel far in order to try them out and apply them communicatively. One of the most famous advocates of the Direct Method was the American Charles Berlitz, whose schools and "Berlitz Method" are now world-renowned., the Direct Method was not without its problems. As Brown points out, "(it) did not take well in public education where the constraints of budget, classroom size, time, and teacher background made such a method difficult to use." By the late 1920s, the method was starting to go into decline and there was even a return to the Grammar Translation Method, which guaranteed more in the way of "scholastic" language learning orientated around reading and grammar skills. But the Direct Method continues to enjoy a popular following in private language school circles, and it was one of the foundations upon which the well-known "Audio-lingual Method" expanded from starting half way through the 20th century.

Audio-Lingual Method

Next "revolution" in terms of language teaching methodology coincided with World War II, when America became aware that it needed people to learn foreign languages very quickly as part of its overall military operations. The "Army Method" was suddenly developed to build communicative competence in translators through very intensive language courses focusing on aural/oral skills. This in combination with some new ideas about language learning coming from the disciplines of descriptive linguistics and behavioral psychology went on to become what is known as the Audio-lingual Method (ALM).new method incorporated many of the features typical of the earlier Direct Method, but the disciplines mentioned above added the concepts of teaching "linguistic patterns" in combination with "habit-forming". This method was one of the first to have its roots "firmly grounded in linguistic and psychological theory", which apparently added to its credibility and probably had some influence in the popularity it enjoyed over a long period of time. It also had a major influence on the language teaching methods that were to follow, and can still

be seen in major or minor manifestations of language teaching methodology even to this day. Factor that accounted for the method's popularity was the "quick success" it achieved in leading learners towards communicative competence. Through extensive mimicry, memorization and "over-learning" of language patterns and forms, students and teachers were often able to see immediate results. This was both its strength and its failure in the long run, as critics began to point out that the method did not deliver in terms of producing long-term communicative ability. Study of linguistics itself was to change, and the area of second language learning became a discipline in its own right.

Silent Way

Addition to "affective" theories relative to language learning, another challenge to the Audio-lingual Method was under way already in the sixties in the form of the "Cognitive Code" and an educational trend known as "Discovery Learning." These concepts most directly challenged the idea that language learning was all about mimicry and good "habit-formation." An emphasis on human cognition in language learning addressed issues such as learners being more responsible for their own learning - formulating independent hypotheses about the "rules" of the target language and testing those hypotheses by applying them and realizing errors. When students create their own sets of meaningful language rules and concepts and then test them out, they are clearly learning through a discovery/exploratory method that is very different from rote-learning. This appears to have much more in common with the way people learn their native language from a very early age, and can account for the way children come out with new language forms and combinations that they have never heard before. The underlying principles here are that learners become increasingly autonomous in, active with and responsible for the learning process in which they are engaged. Gattegno founded "The Silent Way" as a method for language learning in the early 70s, sharing many of the same essential principles as the cognitive code and making good use of the theories underlying Discovery Learning. Some of his basic theories were that "teaching should be subordinated to learning" and "the teacher works with the student; the student works on the language". The most prominent characteristic of the method was that the teacher typically stayed "silent" most of the time, as part of his/her role as facilitator and stimulator, and thus the method's popular name. Language learning is usually seen as a problem solving activity to be engaged in by the students both independently and as a group, and the teacher needs to stay "out of the way" in the process as much as possible. Silent Way is also well-known for its common use of small colored rods of varying length and color-coded word charts depicting pronunciation values, vocabulary and grammatical paradigms. It is a unique method and the first of its kind to really concentrate on cognitive principles in language learning.

COMMONLY USED LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

Activity-based learning: A way of learning by doing activities. The rules of language used in the activity are looked at either after the activity or not at all.

Communicative Approach: A way of teaching based on the principle that learning a language successfully involves communication rather than just memorizing a series of rules. Teachers try to focus on meaningful communication, rather than focusing on accuracy and correcting mistakes all the time.

Content-based learning: When a subject, e.g. mathematics or chemistry is taught in the second language.

Functional Approach: A way of teaching which uses a *syllabus based on functions* rather than on grammatical structures.

Grammar translation method: A way of teaching in which students study grammar and translate words into their own language. They do not practice communication and there is little focus on speaking. A teacher *presents a grammar* rule and vocabulary lists and then students translate a written text from their own language into the second language.

Guided discovery: A way of teaching in which teachers *provide* examples of the target language and then guide the students to *work out* the language *rules* for themselves.

Lexical Approach: A way of analyzing language that is based on *lexical items* such as words, multi-word units, collocations and fixed expressions rather *than grammatical structures*.

Presentation, Practice and Production (PPP): A way of teaching new language in which the teacher *presents* the language, gets students to *practice* it in exercises or other controlled practice activities and then asks students to *use the same language* in a communicative way in their practice.

Situational presentation: A way of *presenting* new language through a simple story or situation. The teacher may use pictures or other *aids* to help them create the situation.

Structural Approach: A way of teaching which uses a *syllabus* based on grammatical structures. Language is presented starting with simple structures and increasing to more complex ones.

Task-based Learning (TBL): A way of teaching in which the teacher gives students meaningful *tasks* to do. The teacher may ask students to think about the language they have used to do the tasks, but the main focus for students is on the task itself. (Project work is an example of TBL)

Test-Teach-Test (TTT): A way of teaching new language in which the teacher asks students to do a *task* without giving them any help, to see how well they know a certain piece of language (*this is the first test*). The teacher then *presents* the new language to the students (*teach*), and finally asks the students to *do another task* using the new language correctly (*this is the second test*).

Total Physical Response: A way of teaching in which the teacher presents language items as instructions and the students have to do exactly what the teacher tells them, e.g. *Open the window! Stand up!* This method is very *meaningful* and good for beginners in the *silent period* when they start to learn a new language.

TEST YOUR KNOWLEDGE

Task-1. For questions 1-7, match the statements with the teaching approaches they describe listed A-H. There is one extra option which you don't need to use.

- A. Functional Approach
- B. Grammar Translation
- C. Lexical Approach
- D. Oral Method
- E. Presentation-Practice-Production (PPP)
- F. Task-based Learning (TBL)
- G. Test-Teach-Test (TTT)
- H. Total Physical Response (TPR)

1. Learners practice new language only after it has been explained by the teacher.
2. The teacher gives comments and the students perform the actions.
3. The teacher assesses the learners' knowledge of the new language before teaching it.
4. The teacher focuses on words and word groups as they are used in real life.
5. Learners write with the use of dictionary.
6. The learners are given an activity to complete, then the teacher talks about the language.
7. The learners study a scripted dialogue then act it out in role plays.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Task-2. For questions 8-14, match the statements with the teaching approaches they describe listed A, B or C.

Teaching Approaches:

- A. Presentation-Practice-Production (PPP)
- B. Task-based Learning (TBL)
- C. Grammar Translation

Statements:

8. Language focus comes after communication activity, so learners know what language they need to practice.
9. Language focus comes first, followed by drills and fluency exercises.
10. Learners improve by trying to communicate authentically.
11. The L1 is mostly used in the classroom.
12. The learners complete a communicative assignment using any English they know.
13. The teacher gives a model for language use before monitoring learners' use.
14. Writing is more important than speaking.

8	9	10	11	12	13	14

Task-3. For questions 15-20, match the statements with the teaching approaches they describe listed A, B or C.

Teaching Approaches:

- A. Total Physical Response (TPR)
- B. Lexical Approach
- C. Test-Teach-Test (TTT)

Statements:

15. The teacher asks students to do a task without giving them any help.
16. The teacher focuses on fixed expressions that occur frequently in spoken language.
17. The learners have to do exactly what the teacher tells them.
18. The teacher asks the learners to do a second task using the new language correctly.
19. The teacher asks the learners to guess the meaning of vocabulary items from context.
20. Learners respond to commands that require physical movement.

15	16	17	18	19	20

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